

hepta coordinated tin with two five membered rings and may be in equilibrium with the structure B [Chart (1)]. Although it is not certain as to which of the structure is stable under what conditions, apparently at low pH values species A is likely to be more stable while at higher pH the other species may be expected to be predominant.

System— $(CH_3)_2SnCl_2$ and Quinalizarin, and Alizarin red S: The data are in conformity with 1 : 1 complex. There are two possibilities of chelation. The chelation may occur from the quinoid oxygen atom and adjacent phenolic oxygen or with the two adjacent phenolic oxygens. The probable arrangements are shown in [Chart (2)].

System— $(CH_3)_2SnCl_2$ and Solochrome black 6-B : From the experimental data it is clear that Solochrome black 6-B behaves as a tridentate Lewis base and its interaction with the Lewis acid $(CH_3)_2SnCl_2$ results in the formation of chelates of structure shown in [Chart (3)] with hepta coordinated tin. The structures containing two rings, one with five members and the other with six members are likely to exist in equilibrium with the other two structures formed by the elimination of HCl molecule. The structures are pH dependent.

System— $(CH_3)_2SnCl_2$ and Methyl oxine : The absorption data of the complexes suggest that the

ligand acts as bidentate chelating agent. Its interaction with $(CH_3)_2SnCl_2$ takes place in the molar ratio 1 : 1. The structure [Chart (4)] may be formulated for the complex which gives rise to hexa coordinated tin atom with five membered ring. Another structure is possible due to the elimination of HCl molecule which is expected in presence of a base. In such a case the mole ratio between Lewis acid and Lewis base would be 1 : 2 which shall be contrary to experimental results.

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (C. S.) is thankful to C. S. I. R., New Delhi for a Junior Research Fellowship.

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Reaction of the Cobaltic Ion. The Kinetics of the Reaction of Cobalt(III) with n-Valeric Acid

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Manuscript received 5 June 1981, revised 2 February 1982, accepted 28 December 1982

THE kinetics of oxidation of a few saturated aliphatic acids with electrolytically prepared cobalt(III) has been studied by Clifford and Waters¹ in methylcyanide-water system. We report here our findings for the reaction of Co(III) with n-valeric acid in aqueous sulphuric acid.

The experimental procedure is similar to the one reported earlier².

Effect of different concentrations of n-valeric and sulphuric acids on the rate of loss of cobalt(III) : The effect of different concentrations of sulphuric acid on the rate of consumption of cobalt(III) in presence of three different concentrations of the organic acid at three temperatures has been investigated. It has been observed that the order of reaction with respect to Co(III) is one as the data could be fitted into the first order rate equation. The order of reaction with respect to the organic acid is fractional.

Chart—Probable structural formulae of complexes.

The average values of the first order rate constants have been incorporated in Table 1.

Temp. °C	Sulphuric acid × (10 ⁻¹ N)	n-valeric acid		
		2.5 × 10 ⁻³ N	5.0 × 10 ⁻³ N	10 × 10 ⁻³ N
		K ₁ × 10 ⁴ min ⁻¹		
20	4.00	1.85	2.48	3.76
	9.00	1.05	1.76	2.47
	19.00	0.70	1.27	1.91
	29.00	0.57	1.10	1.75
	39.00	0.51	1.05	1.65
25	4.00	0.31	4.70	6.99
	9.00	0.18	3.14	4.60
	19.00	1.25	2.50	3.58
	29.00	1.07	2.25	3.25
	39.00	0.97	2.10	3.10
30	4.00	5.31	—	—
	9.00	3.06	5.02	—
	19.00	2.13	3.55	7.82
	29.00	1.80	3.02	5.66
	39.00	1.68	2.76	4.50

Within experimental error the rate of oxidation of n-valeric acid was found to be of the first order with respect to the organic acid and inversely proportional to the concentration of sulphuric acid. The first order rate constants at the given temperatures could be fitted into Michaelis-Menten reciprocal plots, as shown by Fig. 1 and so could be used

Fig. 1

for the separate evaluation of K₁ and k₂ from equation (1)

It can be deduced for a rapid equilibrium that $[(\text{RCO}_2\text{Co}^{3+})] = [\text{Total Co}^{3+}] \cdot K_1 [\text{RCO}_2\text{H}] / ([\text{H}^+] + K_1 [\text{RCO}_2\text{H}])$

where $-d[\text{Co}^{3+}]/dt = K' [\text{Co}^{3+}] = k_2 [\text{Co}^{3+}] \cdot K_1 [\text{RCO}_2\text{H}] / ([\text{H}^+] + K_1 [\text{RCO}_2\text{H}])$

or

$$1/K' = 1/k_2 + [\text{H}^+] / \{k_2 K_1 [\text{RCO}_2\text{H}]\}$$

If the equilibrium (1) was slow, the reaction would be strictly of the first order with respect to Co(III).

Table 1 shows that the experimental data can be fitted to the expression.

$$K' = 0.0476 [\text{valeric acid}] / \{[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4] + 95.13 [\text{valeric acid}]\}$$

when

$$K_1 = 95.13 \text{ and } k_2 = 1.05 \times 10^{-3} \text{ min}^{-1}.$$

The equilibrium constant K₁ varies little with temperature. Thus, the heat of complex formation must be low and the temperature dependence of the oxidation (closely indicative of the oxidation energy needed for the slow decomposition) process (2), i.e.,

followed by steps (3) and (4) as follows :

- (3) $\text{R}^+ + \text{Co}^{3+} \rightarrow \text{R} + \text{Co}^{2+}$
- (4) $\text{R}^+ + \text{H}_2\text{O} \rightarrow \text{R.OH} + \text{H}^+$

The value of K₁ obtained by Clifford and Waters¹ for the oxidation of propionic acid in perchloric acid medium comes out to be 0.72 whereas it is 95.13 in the present case showing a better tendency for complexation in aqueous sulphuric acid.

Effect of temperature : High values of temperature coefficient and positive values of entropy of activation have been the peculiarity of all oxidations effected by cobaltic ions. Thus, for a 10° rise in temperature (between 20 and 30°) the average values of temperature coefficient is 3.03. The average value of energy of activation as calculated from the graph (for 0.40 N sulphuric acid) comes out to be 18.31 k. cal mole⁻¹. Average values of frequency factor, entropy of activation and free energy are 17.76 × 10¹⁶ litres mole⁻¹ sec⁻¹, +19.45 e.u. and 12.01 k.cal mole⁻¹, respectively.

Discussion

The concentration of n-valeric acid has been varied from 0.0025 M to 0.01 M. The rate of loss of cobalt(III) in higher concentrations of sulphuric acid were investigated. The auto-decomposition of cobalt(III) in sulphuric acid of similar strength is at

least twenty times slow as compared to that in presence of the organic acid. The correction for auto-decomposition has, therefore, not been applied. Again, the reaction is of first order with respect to cobalt(III) and fractional with respect to the organic acid whereas it is second order with respect to cobalt(III) in absence of it. Hence, it is clear that the loss of cobaltic ions in presence of *n*-valeric acid is mainly due to its direct oxidation by cobalt(III). It may be mentioned that Clifford and Waters¹ reported the kinetics of the oxidation of propionic acid by cobalt(III). Our observations are similar to their findings.

Hence, for the oxidation of *n*-valeric acid by cobalt(III) also, an inner sphere mechanism involving the rapid reversible formation of a cobaltic complex may be advanced. The complex then breaks down slowly with liberation of free alkyl radical, which then undergoes further rapid reactions. Thus

The formation of a little aldehydic product from *n*-valeric acid was established by the isolation of its 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone.

Acknowledgement

The authors thank Dr. D. D. Sharma, Professor & Head, Department of Post-graduate Studies and Research in Applied Chemistry, Government Engineering College, Jabalpur for encouragement and Professor N. L. Jain, Principal, Government Engineering College Jabalpur, for necessary facilities.

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Kinetics of the Oxidation of Malic Acid by Peroxydisulphate

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Manuscript received 26 December 1975, accepted 25 May 1977

THE kinetics of the oxidation of malic acid by peroxydisulphate ion has been studied by Kumar and Saxena¹ who found the reaction to be bimolecular in the initial stages. A probable free radical mechanism leading to a bimolecular rate law was proposed by these authors according to which the reaction should proceed through $\text{CO}_2\cdot$ radical.

The esr studies of the reaction², however, did not agree with the proposed mechanism of the above authors as no $\text{CO}_2\cdot$ free radical was detected in such systems. The only free radical detected in these systems was $\cdot\text{CH}_2\text{CH}(\text{OH})\text{COO}^-$. This suggests that the mechanism proposed by the above authors should be altered and modified. A new mechanism involving $\cdot\text{CH}_2\text{CH}(\text{OH})\text{COO}^-$ radical is proposed below which leads to the experimental rate law.

According to the above mechanism, the rate of the peroxydisulphate decomposition can be expressed by equation (9)

$$\frac{-d[\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}]}{dt} = k_1[\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}] + k_6[\cdot\text{CH}_2\text{CH}(\text{OH})\text{COO}^-][\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}] \quad (9)$$

On applying the steady state treatment to the above mechanism,

$$\frac{d[\text{SO}_4\cdot^-]}{dt} = \frac{d[\text{O}_2\text{CCH}(\text{OH})\text{COO}_2]}{dt} = \frac{d[\cdot\text{CH}_2\text{CH}(\text{OH})\text{COO}_2]}{dt} = 0$$

the concentration $[\cdot\text{CH}_2\text{CH}(\text{OH})\text{COO}_2]$ can be calculated as

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